

Synthesis, spectral, mass and X-ray diffraction studies of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with Metformin – An oral antidiabetic allopathic drug

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Abstract : Synthesis, spectral characterization and X-ray diffraction studies of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with Metformin an oral antidiabetic drug have been studied. The conductometric titration using monovariation method indicate that complexes are ionic and L₂M type. Analytical data agrees with the molecular formula of complexes viz. [(C₄H₁₁N₅)₂Cu]2Cl and [(C₄H₁₁N₅)₂Zn]2Cl. Structures of complexes assigned are square planar for Metformin – copper and tetrahedral for Metformin-zinc complexes, supported by IR, ¹H NMR and Mass studies and propose structure (1) for complexes. X-Ray diffraction data also supports the formulae and symmetry of complexes.

Keywords : Metformin, oral antidiabetic drugs, complexes, IR, NMR, Mass, X-ray diffraction.

Introduction

In ancient India (before 1000 BC), copper was used in holistic medical science. In *Ayurveda tamra-bhasma*¹ is used in various diseases specifically for bronchitis². Copper performs a vital role in hemopoiesis maintenance of vascular and skeletal integrity and structure of the nervous system³.

Iqbal and co-workers⁴ have synthesized and studied a number of complexes of copper with various antidiabetic drugs. Copper tetracycline (2 : 1) complex has been studied by Banet and Goyan⁵.

Janabi *et al.*,⁶ have studied copper complexes with various antimalarials. Sharma *et al.*,⁷ studied biological activity of mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} and their effect on some bacteria and fungi.

Zinc is an essential trace mineral, so we get it through the food we eat. Next to iron, zinc is most common mineral in the body and is found in every plant and animal cell⁸. It has been used since ancient times to heal wounds and plays an important role in the immune system, reproduction, growth, vision, blood clotting, proper insulin and thyroid function^{9,10}.

Chelates of streptomycin are obtained by adding aque-

ous solutions of zinc salts to the solution of streptomycin at pH 9.0 (*loc.cit*). Zinc complexes of sulpha drugs have been prepared and studied by Salil *et al.*¹¹, Bipin *et al.*¹², Sharma *et al.*¹³, Iqbal and co-workers^{14–16,33} have synthesized and studied of zinc complexes with antidiabetic drugs and have attempted to compare the antidiabetic properties of zinc complexes within the parent drugs.

Sterne was the first to try Metformin on humans for the treatment of diabetes; he coined the name. Glucophage (glucose eater) for the drug and published his result in 1957^{17,18}.

Metformin is sold under several trade names, including Glucophage XR, Riomet, Fortamet, Glumetza, obimed, Gludormin, Diarber, Diaber, and Diaformin, Broad interest in Metformin was not rekindled until the withdrawal of the other biguanides in the 1970s.

Generic formulations are now available in several countries and Metformin is believed to have become the most widely prescribed antidiabetic drug in the world.

Therefore looking the importance of Metformin, we have studied Metformin complexes with Cu and Zn.

The results of these investigations are presented herein.

Experimental

Ligand-metal ratio :

(a) Pure “Metformin” (m.p. 236 °C), 0.005 M, were diluted to 200 ml each and titrated conductometrically against copper chloride and zinc chloride at 29 ± 1 °C. Results were plotted in the form of graph which indicates that copper form complex (1 : 1 and 2 : 1) ligand metal ratio (L_2M and ML) and zinc form only in 2 : 1 ligand metal ratio (L_2M).

(b) Formation of 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 (L_2M) ratio was also confirmed by Job’s method¹⁹ of continuous variation as modified by Turner and Anderson²⁰, using absorbance as index property, from these values the stability constant ($\log k$) and free energy change ($-\Delta F$), were also calculated (Irving and Rossotti²¹⁻²³, Iqbal *et al.*²⁴⁻²⁶, Willard *et al.*²⁷). Figs. 1 and 2 given for “Metformin” copper and zinc complexes.

Synthesis of complexes :

The chemicals used in this synthesis were all of analytical grade E. Merck. A weighed quantity of “Metformin” (2 mol) was dissolved separately in minimum quantity of 90% ethanol. The copper and zinc solution was prepared by dissolving separately in the same solvent. Ligand solution was added slowly with stirring into the solution of metallic salt at room temperature; maintain the pH between 6.0 to 6.5 by adding dilute NaOH solution. Copper form two complex in 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 ratio at pH 6.5 and 9.5 respectively. On refluxing the mixture for 3–4 h and on cooling the complexes separated out, which were filtered off, washed well with ethanol and finally dried in vacuum and weighed.

The elemental analyses of the isolated complexes were carried out using Coleman Analyzer at the Departmental Microanalytical Laboratory, CDRI, Lucknow. Chloride

Fig. 1. Job’s method of continuous variation for Metformin-copper complex (modified by Turner and Anderson).

Fig. 2. Job’s method of continuous variation for Metformin-zinc complex (modified by Turner and Anderson).

was determined gravimetrically. Copper and zinc analysis was carried out in Qualichem Laboratory, Nagpur by atomic absorption spectroscopy.

The IR spectra of the ligand as well as of the complexes was recorded on B-OMEM-FTIR (USA), ¹H NMR spectra of the ligand and isolated complexes were recorded on a Bruker AM-200 spectrometer and DMSO-*d*₆ was used as a solvent. IR and ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in CDRI, Lucknow, India.

X-Ray diffractometer model Rigaku D-max/B with 12 KW rotating for X-Ray studies. Anode X-ray generator was used for scanning the ligand. Metal salts and respective complexes at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh, India. The radiation used was Cu, K α (1W = 1.5060 Å). The samples were scanned in the range 10.0084 to 79.9804 (2 θ) powder data were indexes using computer software (FPSUIT V 2.0).

From stoichiometry and analytical data, the composition of the complex comes out to be [(C₄H₁₀N₅)₂·Cu]2Cl and [(C₄H₁₀N₅)₂·Zn]2Cl, which favors 2 : 1 (L₂M) ratio. The tentative structure (1) assigned to complexes on the basis of analytical data, was further supported by XRD-data, Cullity²⁸, Duval²⁹, Bragg and Bragg³⁰, Guinier³¹, Henry *et al.*²⁴, Kidwai³³.

Mass spectra of (MF)₂Cu and (MF)₂Zn complexes was recorded at CDRI, Lucknow, India which provides information about the complexes by examination of the fragmentation pattern and total mass of the complex. Proposed structures (1) for the isolated complexes are also supported by mass spectral studies of Mc Cullagh *et al.*³⁴, Bayliss and Lashin³⁵, Windig *et al.*³⁶, Andrew³⁷, Mc Lafferty³⁸, Iqbal *et al.*³⁹.

Results and discussion

Physicochemical characteristics of "Metformin"-copper complex :

Molecular formula [(C₄H₁₁N₅)₂Cu]2Cl, Mol. wt : 392.65; Colour : pink; Yield : 50%; m.p. 280 °C; C, 24.48 (25.82); H, 5.60 (5.64); N, 35.67 (34.85); Metal, 16.18 (18.96), Cl⁻, 18.06 (17.85).

Physicochemical characteristics of "Metformin"-zinc complex :

Molecular formula [(C₄H₁₁N₅)₂Zn]2Cl, Mol. wt : 394.39, Colour : white; Yield : 55%; m.p. 260 °C; C,

27.50 (27.83), H, 6.30 (5.04); N, 40.06 (41.86); Metal, 18.71 (18.94); Cl⁻, 20.34 (20.10).

Electronic spectral studies :

In Cu^{II} complex of "Metformin" the observed magnetic moment is 1.86 and bands observed at 380 cm⁻¹ attributed to charge transfer while the value 550 cm⁻¹ and 650 cm⁻¹ are assignment to the ²T_{2g} → 2E_g and ²T_{2g}(F) → 2E_g transition respectively suggest a square planar environment around "Metformin"-Cu^{II} complex. "Metformin"-Zn^{II} complex are found diamagnetic as expected from d¹⁰ system and may have tetrahedral geometry.

Infra-red spectral studies :

The IR spectra of ligand and isolated complexes were recorded within the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹. Assignments of the infrared spectral bands are based on literature. IR spectrum shows important bands due to ν (M-N) 500 ± 10 cm⁻¹, ν (C-N-C) 670 ± 10 cm⁻¹, ν (-N-H) 1426 ± 20 cm⁻¹, ν (-N-H) 1630 ± 20 cm⁻¹, (amine salt) 2380 ± 20 cm⁻¹, ν (C-H) 3020 ± 20 cm⁻¹, ν (N-H) 3275 ± 20 cm⁻¹, ν (N-H) 3520 ± 20 cm⁻¹. The proposed structure for the isolated complexes is also supported by IR absorptions (Cotton⁴⁰, Rao⁴¹, Nakamoto⁴², Bellamy⁴³ and Weissberger⁴⁴).

¹H NMR studies :

¹H NMR spectral data it was observed that a singlet due to the imide (NH) proton around (δ 8.74) in the spectrum of the ligand and found less broad band in complexes. This also confirms the deprotonation of imide NH group through enolization (the appearance of >C=N stretching band observed in IR spectra).

Assignment of "Metformin"-copper complex, molecular formula [(C₄H₁₁N₅)₂Cu]2Cl (molecular weight = 392.65) : δ 7.207 (due to amine salt), 6.788 (2H, s, 1C=NH, 1C-NH-C, *J* 2.014 Hz), 2.912 (6H, s, 2 methyl-CH₃ *J* 3.134 Hz), 2.49 (s), 3.369 (s). Residual solvent and water of solvent of the DMSO-*d*₆ respectively.

Assignment of "Metformin"-zinc complex, molecular formula [(C₄H₁₁N₅)₂Zn]2Cl (molecular mass = 394.39) : δ 7.207 (2H, s, 1-NH, 1-HCl), 6.788 (3H, s, 1C=NH, 1C-H-C, *J* 2.014 Hz), 2.912 (6H, s, 2 methyl-CH₃ *J* 3.134 Hz), 2.49 (s), 3.369 (s). Residual solvent and water of solvent of the DMSO-*d*₆ respectively. The proposed structure for the isolated complexes is also sup-

ported by Slichter⁴⁵, Akit⁴⁶, Siewers⁴⁷, Dury *et al.*⁴⁸, Rathod *et al.*⁴⁹, Jacob and Iqbal *et al.*⁵⁰, Afridi⁵¹, Budhani *et al.*⁵².

Mass spectral studies :

Mass spectrum of the compound is a plot which represents the intensities of the signals at various m/z values. It is highly characteristic of the compound that no two compounds can have similar mass spectra. It provides information regarding the molecular structure of organic and inorganic compounds. In present paper we studied the "Metformin" complexes of copper and zinc and assignments are : molecular formula of "Metformin"-copper complex $[(C_4H_{11}N_5)_2Cu]2Cl$, (Mol. wt. = 392.45), m/z 390 due to $[(C_4H_{11}N_5)_2Cu.2Cl]^+$ or $(ML_2)^+$. Molecular ion peak (m^+); m/z 130 due to $[C_4H_{12}N_5]^+$, base peak ion 100% relative abundance, m/z 295 due to $[(C_4H_7N_4)_2Cu]^+$ radical ion.

Molecular formula of "Metformin"-zinc complex $[(C_4H_{11}N_5)_2Zn]2Cl$, Mol. wt. = 349.39, m/z 371 may due to $[(C_4H_{11}N_5)_2Zn]Cl_2]^+$ or $(ML_2)^+$. Molecular ion peak (m^+); m/z 130 due to $[C_4H_{12}N_5]^+$, base peak ion 100% relative abundance. m/z 88 due to $[C_3H_9N_3]^+$ fragment ion.

X-Ray diffraction studies :

X-Ray diffraction studies also support the complex and formation of new bonds⁵³⁻⁵⁶. The number of peaks in Metformin are 13 while that of "Metformin"-copper and "Metformin"-zinc complexes are 15 and 15 as shown in X-ray diffractogram (Figs. 3 and 4) respectively and indicating that complexes formed are a well knit one,

moreover all the reflections are new ones and the patterns are fairly strong. On comparing the pattern obtained with available literature, it is evident that its pattern is not in good agreement with available information and thus confirms the formation of totally new complexes. The X-ray pattern have been indexed by using computer software (FPSUIT 2.0V) and applying interactive trial and error method keeping in mind the characteristics of the various symmetry system, till a good fit was obtained between the observed and the calculated $\sin^2 \theta$ value. The unit cell parameters were calculated from the indexed data, from cell data and crystal lattice parameters of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} indicates complexes attributed to orthorhombic crystal system. Powder X-ray diffraction patterns indicate that the synthesized complexes are orthorhombic structure. The particle size is 11.35 nm of "Metformin"-copper and 5.90 nm of "Metformin"-zinc complex respectively, which is calculated from X-ray line broadening using the Scherrer formula $Dhkl = \kappa\lambda/\beta hkl \cos \theta$, where D is the particle diameter in ångstroms, κ is a coefficient and is equal to 0.89 here, β is the half-maximum line width, and λ is the wavelength of X-rays, porosity is 0.041 and 0.022 calculated by formula

$$\frac{d_{true} - d_{obs} \times 100}{d_{tru}}$$

and volume of the unit cell is 14066, 14044 is calculated by volume (Å^3), = abc where a , b and c are lattice parameters. Density = $\frac{\text{Weight}}{\text{Volume}}$ is found 0.0282 g/cm^3 , 0.0280 g/cm^3 for "Metformin"-copper and

Fig. 3. X-Ray diffractogram of MF-Cu Complex.

Fig. 4. X-Ray diffractogram of MF-Zn complex.

“Metformin”-zinc complexes respectively. Space group is *Pm3m* and $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 90^\circ$, $\gamma = 90^\circ$.

Discussion

For supporting the proposed structure of copper and zinc complexes with “Metformin” initially Job’s method of continuous variation as modified by Turner and Anderson was conducted which indicate 2 : 1 ligand : metal ratio of the complexes, moreover stability constant and free energy change was also calculated. Analytical data agree to the molecular formula $[(C_4H_{11}N_5)_2Cu]2Cl$ and $[(C_4H_{11}N_5)_2Zn]2Cl$.

The proposed structure for Cu and Zn complexes of “Metformin” was further supported from spectroscopic methods like IR, ¹H NMR, Electronic spectra and mass spectral studies *etc.* Molar conductance values of the com-

plex supports the ionic structure of the complexes. The biguanidine unit inside the coordination sphere has a positive charge while Cl⁻ occupies the outer place of the coordination sphere.

The IR spectral assignment like M-N and the linkage of N⁵ to the metal through the covalent bond by the replacement of hydrogen from N⁵, while coordinate bond is from N¹ to the metal ion. Moreover, the difference in the NMR peak of the drug (wide peak) and the complex (narrow peak) are further supporting the removal of one of the “H” from the N-H group.

Electronic spectra and mass spectral results and values are further supporting the coordination of Zn/Cu with nitrogen atom of the drug.

A detailed study of X-ray also supports the complexes formation and the various values like particle size, porosity, volume of unit cell, density as well as crystal system was evaluated and discussed.

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